

Acarorum Catalogus I – First supplement (2008–2016)

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Abstract. The monograph of BERON (2008) is completed with the data in 166 papers published between 2008 and 2016 (some of them in 2017), or omitted. Many new taxa have been published, other taxa have been synonymized or altered, mostly by specialists from Germany, Poland, Iran, Spain, Montenegro, Ukraine, Bulgaria, and other countries. Now (by August 2017) are recognized (some of them gen. or sp. inquire.) one genus and nine recent sp. of Calyptostomatidae, 10 genera and 56 sp. of Smarididae and 57 genera and more than 850 sp. of Erythraeidae.

Key words: Catalogus, supplements, Calyptostomatoidea, Calyptostomatidae, Erythraeoidea, Erythraeidae, Smarididae

Introduction

After the publication of the first volume of the series *Acarorum Catalogus* (BERON, 2008), many new papers have been published by R. Haitlinger, P. Beron, J. Mąkol, G. Gabryś, M. Kamran, J. Łaydanowicz, A. Wohltmann, J.G. Mayoral, P. Barranco, M. Šundić, A. Khaustov and especially by the very active Iranian group of researchers (A. Saboori, S. Ahmadi, H. Hajiqanbar, M. Khanjani, M. Akrami, M. Bagheri, M. Hakimitabar and others). New genera and species have been described (almost all based on larvae, mostly from Iran, Montenegro and Spain), several other taxonomic changes took place and new synonymes were created. A few papers have been omitted from the Bibliography. This situation requires an updating of my Catalogue. Meanwhile has been published the Checklist of terrestrial Parasitengonae of MĄKOL & WOHLTMANN (2012, 2013).

The author is very grateful to Prof. Joanna Mąkol for the reading and correcting the MS of this supplement.

New genera (valid), described since 2008, or altered:

Colleboerythraeus Noei, Saboori et Hakimitabar, 2017

Makolia Saboori, Khaustov et Hakimitabar, 2009

Iraniella Karimi- Iravanlou, Kamali et Talebi, 2002

Neomomorangia Fain et Santiago-Blay – full generic status

Madinahustium Kamran et Alatawi, 2016

Marantelophus Haitlinger, 2011

Monteustium Haitlinger et Šundić, 2015

Nagoricanelia Haitlinger, 2009

Pukakia Clark, 2014

Pararainbowia Dunlop, 2010

Synonymized genera (partly as a result of rearing of larvae):

Zhangiella Saboori, Cobanoglu et Bayram, 2007, syn. f. *Curteria* Southcott, 1961

Abalakeus Southcott, 1994 = *Eatoniana* Cambridge, 1898

Hauptmannia Oudemans, 1910 = *Abrolophus* Berlese, 1891

Clipeosoma Southcott, 1948 = *Hirstiosoma* Womersley, 1934

Pilosoma Southcott, 1961 = *Fessonina* von Heyden, 1826

Guatustium Haitlinger, 2000 = *Balaustium* von Heyden, 1826

Palenquustium Haitlinger, 2000 = *Balaustium* von Heyden, 1826

As a result of the recent contributions, the number of genera and species in Calyptostomatoidea and Erythraeoidea (some of them uncertain status) is updated as follows:

Calyptostomatidae – one genus, nine sp.

Smarididae – 10 genera, 56 sp.

Erythraeidae – 57 genera, more than 850 sp.

New contributions to the Catalogue:

Fam. Calyptostomatidae

Calyptostoma giuliae Haitlinger et Šundić (larval)

Calyptostoma giuliae HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 920

Type locality: Cambodia

Distribution: Cambodia

Host: from herbaceous plants

Calyptostoma gorganica Saboori et Soukhtsaraii, in SABOORI, SOUKHTSARAII, YAZDANIAN, GOLPAYEGANI (2012)(larval)

Calyptostoma gorganica Saboori et Soukhtsaraii, in SABOORI, SOUKHTSARAII, YAZDANIAN & GOLPAYEGANI, 2012: 37

Type locality: Shast Kalateh forest, Gorgan City, Golestan prov.

Distribution: Iran

Host: *Limonia caucasica* (Diptera: Tipulidae)

Calyptostoma marantica Haitlinger et Šundić (larval)

Calyptostoma marantica HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 923

Type locality: Sulawesi

Distribution: Indonesia

Host: from herbaceous plants

Calyptostoma latisetata (Shiba, 1976) – New Caledonia, Tasmania (MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013)

Calyptostoma velutinum (Müller, 1776) – Montenegro (ŠUNDIĆ & HAITLINGER, 2015: 188); Serbia, Sicily (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Species inquirendae (see MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013):

Calyptostoma exculpta (Berlese, 1916)

Calyptostoma neoguineana (Canestrini, 1897)

Fam. Smarididae

Smaridinae

Smaris maraghehiensis Saboori et Bagheri (ad.)

Smaris maraghehiensis SABOORI & BAGHERI, 2011: 105

Type locality: Maragheh, 1450 m, East Azarbaijan Province

Distribution: Iran

Hirstiosomatinae

Hirstiosoma latreillei (Grandjean, 1947)

(syn. *Clipeosoma jupiter* Southcott, 1948) – Finland (GABRYŚ, ROLAND, MAKOL & LEHTINEN, 2009); Iran (NOEI, SABOORI, etc., 2013)

Hirstiosoma amfilohije Haitlinger et Šundić (larval)

Hirstiosoma amfilohije HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2017: 1411

Type locality: Korita Kučka (1200 m)

Distribution: Montenegro

Hirstiosoma Womersley, 1934 is the adult stage of *Clipeosoma* Southcott, 1948; *Pilosoma* Southcott, 1961 is the larval form of *Fessonina* von Heyden, 1826 (WOHLTMANN, 2010)

Fessonina papillosa (Hermann, 1804) – Iran (NOEI, SABOORI, etc., 2013); China (LI & FAN, 1997)

Fessonina torshizica Salarzahi et Hajiqanbar

Fessonina torshizica SALARZEHİ & HAJIQANBAR, 2012: 18

Type locality: Torshiz, Khorasan Razavi province, 1215 m a.s.l.

Distribution: Iran

Sphaerotarsus baenai Mayoral et Barranco (larval)

Sphaerotarsus baenai MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2017: 623

Type locality: Vereda de los Labrados, Villa Manrique

Distribution: Spain

Host: on soil

Fam. Erythraeidae

Erythraeinae

Genus *Collemboerythraeus* Noei, Saboori et Hakimitabar

Collemboerythraeus Noei, Saboori & Hakimitabar, 2017:

Type species: *Collemboerythraeus vosoughae* Noei, Saboori et Hakimitabar, 2017

Collemboerythraeus vosoughae Noei, Saboori et Hakimitabar

Collemboerythraeus vosoughae Noei, Saboori & Hakimitabar, 2017:

Type locality: Jahrom City, Fars Province

Distribution: Iran

Host: undet. Collembola, Sminthuridae

Eatoniana gonabadensis (Ahmadi, Hajiqanbar et Saboori) (larval)

Abalakeus gonabadensis AHMADI, HAJIQANBAR & SABOORI, 2012: 170

Type locality: Gonabad, Khorasan Razavi prov.

Distribution: Iran

Hosts: *Aphis craccivora* (Homoptera: Aphididae);

Dociostaurus cf. tartarus (Orthoptera: Acrididae)

Eatoniana plumipes (L. Koch, 1856)

Abalakeus jahromiensis SEDGHI, SABOORI & HAKIMITABAR, 2010: 432 (synonymized with *Eatoniana plumipes* by MAKOL & SEVSAY, 2015)

Type locality: Jahrom

Distribution: Iran (for *A. jahromiensis*); Dumlu, Erzurum prov. (Turkey, for *E. plumipes*)

Host: undet. nymph of Pentatomidae (Heteroptera) and on soil (for *A. jahromiensis*)

Curteria episcopalis (C.L. Koch, 1837) – Finland (GABRYŚ et al., 2009)

The genus *Zhangia* Saboori, Cobanoglu et Bayram, 2007 was synonymized with *Curteria* Southcott, 1961 by SABOORI, KHAUSTOV, HAKIMITABAR & HAJIQANBAR (2009: 29).

Abalakeus Southcott, 1994 became junior synonym of *Eatoniana* Cambridge, 1898 (MAKOL & SEVSAY, 2015). A female of *Eatoniana plumipes* (L. Koch, 1856) was selected as neotype.

Abalakeus jahromiensis Sedghi, Saboori et Hakimitabar, 2010 syn. of *Eatoniana plumipes*

Abalakeus bambusae Zhang, Zhang et Lin, 2000 becomes *Eatoniana bambusae* (Zhang, Zhang et Lin)

Abalakeus chekei Southcott, 1994 becomes *Eatoniana chekei* (Southcott)

Abalakeus lorestanicus Saboori et Lachinani, 2003 becomes *Eatoniana lorestanica* (Saboori et Lachinani)

Abalakeus gonabadensis Ahmadi, Hajiqanbar et Saboori, 2012 becomes *Eatoniana gonabadensis* (Ahmadi, Hajiqanbar et Saboori)

All these species were transferred to *Eatoniana* at synonymization (note of J. Makol)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) adanaensis Saboori et Cobanoglu (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) adanaensis SABOORI & COBANOGLU, 2010: 250; AZIMI, SABOORI & SHIRDEL, 2011: 51

Type locality: Adana

Distribution: Iran, Turkey

Host: unknown

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) albanicus Haitlinger (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) albanicus HAITLINGER, 2012: 340; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 40

Type locality: Shënavasi nr. Sarandë

Distribution: Albania

Host: herbaceous plant

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) ankaraicus Saboori, Çobanoğlu et Bayram, 2004 – Montenegro (SABOORI, PEŠIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2008)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) aphidivorous Šundić, Haitlinger, Michaud et Colares (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) aphidivorous ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER, MICHAUD & COLARES, 2015: 43

Type locality: Hays, Kansas

Distribution: USA (Kansas)

Host: *Melanaphis sacchari* (Hemiptera: Aphididae)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) capeverdensis Haitlinger (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) capeverdensis HAITLINGER, 2009a: 1154

Type locality: Sal Island, three km north of Espargos (16°47'N, 22°57')

Distribution: Cape Verde

Host: Unknown; collected from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) cinereus (Dugès) = *E. similis* (Canestrini)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) chrysoperlae Khanjani, Mirmoayedi, Fayaz et Sharifian (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) chrysoperlae KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, FAYAZ & SHARIFIAN, 2012: 63

Type locality: Shahanjarin, Razan, Hamedan Province

Distribution: Iran

Host: *Chrysoperla kolthoffi* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) elmalicus Haitlinger (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) elmalicus HAITLINGER, 2010: 53

Type locality: Elmali, 1200 m

Distribution: Turkey

Host: from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) etnaensis Heitlinger
Erythraeus (Erythraeus) etnaensis HEITLINGER, 2011: 291

Type locality: Etna

Distribution: Sicily

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) gertrudae Haitlinger, 1987 – Austria (HAITLINGER, 2009a). Syn. of *E. regalis* (C.L. Koch), acc. to STÄLSTEDT et al., 2016.

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) gorcensis Gabryś

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) gorcensis GABRYŚ,

2016: 1 (pro *E. acis* sensu Schweizer, 1951)

Type locality: Switzerland

Distribution: Switzerland

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) hilariae Haitlinger (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) hilariae HAITLINGER,

2010: 50

Type locality: Elmali, 1200 m

Distribution: Turkey

Host: from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) jowitae Haitlinger, 1987 – Sweden (HAITLINGER, 2008c), Romania, Macedonia (HAITLINGER, 2009d). Syn. of *E. cinereus* (Dugès), acc. to STÅLSTEDT et al., 2016.

Erythraeus (E.) kuyperi (Oudemans, 1910) – Estonia, Lithuania (HAITLINGER, 2010a). Syn. of *E. regalis* (C.L. Koch), acc. to STÅLSTEDT et al., 2016.

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) layyahensis Kamran, Afzal et Bashir (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) layyahensis [KAMRAN, 2009: 48] KAMRAN, AFZAL & BASHIR, 2013: 35

Type locality: Punjab, 22 km east of district Layyah

Distribution: Pakistan

Host: from grass

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) loomerus Kamran (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) loomerus KAMRAN, 2009: 55

Type locality: Punjab

Distribution: Pakistan

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) mirabi Khanjani, Ueckermann et Ul-Hassan (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) mirabi KHANJANI, UECKERMANN & UL-HASSAN, 2012: 52

Type locality: Iran

Distribution: Iran

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) picaforticus Haitlinger, 2002 – Sicily (HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2013)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) pistacicus Haitlinger, Mehrnejad et Šundić (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) pistacicus HAITLINGER, MEHRNEJAD & ŠUNDIĆ, 2016: 804; HAITLINGER R., MEHRNEJAD M. REZA, 2017: 320

Type locality: Rafsanjan, Raviz

Distribution: Iran

Hosts: [collected from *Pistacia atlantica mutica* (Anacardiaceae)]; *Agonoscena pistaciae* (Homoptera, Psyllidae); *Farsiana pistaciae* (Hemiptera: Miridae)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) populi Khanjani, Mirmoayed, Fayaz et Sharifian (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) populi KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, FAYAZ & SHARIFIAN, 2012: 54

Type locality: Hamedan, 1828 m, Hamedan Province

Distribution: Iran

Host: *Stephanitis pyri* (Heteroptera: Tingidae)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) serbicus Šundić, Haitlinger et Hakimitabar

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) serbicus ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER & HAKIMITABAR, 2015: 788

Type locality: Serbia

Distribution: Serbia

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) shojaii Babolmorad et Saboori, 2000 – Pakistan (KAMRAN, 2009)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) sicilicus Haitlinger
Erythraeus (Erythraeus) sicilicus HAITLINGER, 2011: 291

Type locality: Sicily

Distribution: Sicily

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) smolyanensis Haitlinger (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) smolyanensis HAITLINGER, 2009d: 52; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 40

Type locality: Smolyan, Bulgaria

Distribution: Bulgaria, Montenegro

Host: from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) southcotti Goldarazena et Zhang, 1998 – Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) uhadi Kamran et Alatawi (larval)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) uhadi KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2014a: 79

Type locality: Uhad Mt, Al-Madina

Distribution: Saudi Arabia

Host: *Opseius* sp. (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae)

Erythraeus (Erythraeus) walii Kamran (larval)
Erythraeus (Erythraeus) walii KAMRAN, 2009: 41

Type locality: Punjab

Distribution: Pakistan

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) adrianicus Haitlinger

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) adrianicus HAITLINGER, 2012: 137

Type locality: Palazzo Adriano n. Sciacca

Distribution: Sicily

Host: from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) arminouensis

Haitlinger et Łupicki

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) arminouensis
HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2011: 405

Type locality: Arminou

Distribution: Cyprus

Host: from herbaceous herbs

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) aydinicus Saboori,

Cakmak et Nouri-Gonbalani, 2004 – Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) bibadakiensis

Haitlinger

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) bibadakiensis
HAITLINGER, 2011: 48

Type locality: Bibadaki Island n. Labuan Bajo, Flores

Distribution: Indonesia

Host: from herbaceous herbs

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) budapestensis Fain

et Ripka, 1998 – Montenegro (SABOORI, PEŠIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2008), Turkey (HAITLINGER, 2010b); Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012); Albania (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

E. (Z.) preciosus Goldarazena & Zhang, 1998; **syn.** by HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 585

E. (Z.) ueckermanni Saboori, Nowzari et Bagheri-Zenouz, 2004; **syn.** by HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 585

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) coleopterus Mortazavi, Hajiqanbar et Saboori

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) coleopterus MORTAZAVI, HAJIQANBAR & SABOORI, 2012: 110

Type locality: Ghanat Chenar village, Sirjan city, Kerman province, southeastern Iran (29° 52' 33" N, 55° 43' 56" E, 2253 m a.s.l.)

Distribution: Iran

Host: *Cyphonoxia* sp. (Coleoptera: Scarabaeidae)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) eleonora Haitlinger,

1987 – Poland, neotype (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) hafezi Saboori,

Hakimitabar et Mahmoudi (larval)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) hafezi SABOORI, HAKIMITABAR & MAHMOUDI, 2014: 80

Type locality: Shiraz city, Fars Province

Distribution: Iran

Host: undet. (Heteroptera: Cicadidae)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) hamedanicus

Khanjani, Mirmoayedi, Nahad et Fayaz (larval)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) hamedanicus KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, NAHAD & FAYAZ, 2010: 26

Synonyme of *E. (Z.) ueckermanni* Saboori, Nowzari et Bagheri-Zenouz, 2004 (**syn.** by MAHMOUDI et al., 2011)

Type locality: Hamedan

Distribution: Iran

Host: *Pyrrhocoris apterus* (Heteroptera: Pyrrhocoridae)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) lancifer Southcott,

1995 – Saudi Arabia (KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2014a)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) longipedus Saboori et

Nowzari, 2001 – Pakistan (KAMRAN, 2009)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) monrealicus Haitlinger

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) monrealicus
HAITLINGER, 2012: 140

Type locality: Monreale n. Palermo

Distribution: Sicily

Host: from herbaceous plants

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) passidonicus

Haitlinger, 2006 – Turkey (HAITLINGER, 2010b)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) cf. ueckerman-

ni Saboori, Nowzari et Bagheri-Zenouz, 2004 – Montenegro (SABOORI, PEŠIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2008)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) perpusillus Kamran, Afzal, Raza, Irfanullah, Bashir et Ahmad (larval)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) perpusillus KAMRAN, AFZAL, RAZA, IRFANULLAH, BASHIR & AHMAD, 2009: 358

Type locality: 5 km south of district Okara (Punjab)

Distribution: Pakistan

Host: *Pyrilla perpusilla* (Homoptera: Lophopidae)

Erythraeus (Zaracarus) ruizporterae Mayoral

et Barranco (larval)

- Erythraeus (Zaracarus) ruizporterae* MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2008: 114
Type locality: Yeso de Sorbas (Almeria)
Distribution: Spain
- Erythraeus (Zaracarus) soleimanii* Khanjani, Mirmoayedi, Nahad et Fayaz (larval)
Erythraeus (Zaracarus) soleimanii KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, NAHAD & FAYAZ, 2010: 21
Type locality: Razan, Hamedan
Distribution: Iran
Host: *Chrysoperla kolthoffi* (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae)
- Erythraeus (Zaracarus) tuzicus* Haitlinger et Šundić
Erythraeus (Zaracarus) tuzicus HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 190
Type locality: Tuzi near Podgorica
Distribution: Montenegro
Host: from herbaceous plants
- Erythrithes otamahua* Clark
Erythrithes otamahua CLARK, 2013: 394
Type locality: New Zealand
Distribution: New Zealand
- Forania sendrai* Mayoral et Barranco (larval)
Forania sendrai MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2010: 62
Type locality: Sierra Alhamilla, T.M. Turrilas, Almeria
Distribution: Spain
Host: *Tapinoma* sp. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)
- Kamertonina polonica* Gabryś – Finland (GABRYŚ et al., 2009)
- Lasioerythraeus cardonensis* Haitlinger (larval)
Lasioerythraeus cardonensis HAITLINGER, 2008b: 63
Type locality: Cardon, Margerita Island
Distribution: Venezuela
Host: from herbaceous plants
- Lasioerythraeus saboorii* Khanjani, Raisi et Izadi (larval)
Lasioerythraeus saboorii KHANJANI, RAISI & IZADI, 2011: 546
Type locality: Boshrowyeh, Ferdous City, South Khorassan Prov.
Distribution: Iran
Host: *Aphis punicae* (Homoptera: Aphididae)
- Lasioerythraeus setarius* Kamran et Bashir (larval)
Lasioerythraeus setarius KAMRAN & BASHIR, 2013: 722
Type locality: 22 km east of district Layyah (Punjab, Pakistan)
Distribution: Pakistan
Host: from foxtail grass (*Setaria viridis* L.)
- Genus *Makolia* Saboori, Khaustov et Hakimitabar (larval)
Makolia SABOORI, KHAUSTOV & HAKIMITABAR, 2009: 23
Type species: *Makolia crimeaensis* Saboori, Khaustov et Hakimitabar, 2009
- Makolia crimeaensis* Saboori, Khaustov et Hakimitabar (larval)
Makolia crimeaensis SABOORI, KHAUSTOV & HAKIMITABAR, 2009: 24
Type locality: Crimea, Ay-Petri mountain pasture
Distribution: Crimea
Host: *Lasius* sp. (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)
- Phanolophinae** – according to WELBOURN (1991), BERON (2008), WOHLTMANN (2010), belongs to Erythraeidae
- Phanolophus oedipodarum* André, 1927 – Yemen, Germany (WOHLTMANN (2010))
- Genus *Iraniella* Karimi Iravanlou, Kamali et Talebi
Iraniella KARIMI IRAVANLOU, KAMALI & TALEBI, 2002: 124
Type species: *Iraniella moharrampuri* Karimi Iravanlou, Kamali et Talebi, 2002
- Iraniella moharrampuri* Karimi Iravanlou, Kamali et Talebi (larval)
Iraniella moharrampuri KARIMI IRAVANLOU, KAMALI & TALEBI, 2002: 124
Type locality: Iran
Distribution: Iran
- Leptinae**
MAKOL, GABRYŚ & ŁAYDANOWICZ (2011) “resurrected” and re-described *Leptus phalangii* (De Geer, 1778) (the type-species of genus *Leptus* Latreille) and synonymized under this species *Leptus nemorum* (C.L. Koch, 1836) and *L. beroni* Fain, 1991.
- Leptus (L.) aphidus* Kamran (larval)

- Leptus (L.) aphidus* KAMRAN, 2009: 66
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan
- Leptus (L.) astrubali* Haitlinger, 1999 – Nepal (HAITLINGER, 2009d)
- Leptus (L.) biljanae* Šundić et Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (L.) biljanae ŠUNDIĆ & HAITLINGER, 2015: 188
Type locality: Župa, Nikšić, Montenegro
Distribution: Montenegro
Host: from Orthoptera indet.
- Leptus (L.) brasiliicus* Haitlinger, Šundić et Pompermaier (larval)
Leptus (L.) brasiliicus HAITLINGER, ŠUNDIĆ & POMPERMAIER, 2017: 879
Type locality: 30 km NE of Brasilia
Distribution: Brazil
- Leptus (L.) cabareticus* Haitlinger, 2004 – Guadeloupe (HAITLINGER, 2011b)
- Leptus (L.) canaricus* Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (L.) canaricus HAITLINGER, 2009b: 148
Type locality: Tenerife, Las Cañadas, Fuente Joco
Distribution: Canary Islands
Hosts: *Laparocerus crassifrons*, *L. tessellates* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)
- Leptus (L.) chiusicus* Haitlinger et Šundić (larval)
Leptus (L.) chiusicus HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2014b: 1509
Type locality: Sicilia
Distribution: Sicilia
- Leptus (L.) danelli* Southcott, 1992 raised to species (formerly *L. ignotus danelli*)(ŁAYDANOWICZ & MAKOL, 2010)
- Leptus (L.) delijanensis* Khademi, Saboori et Hakimitabar (larval)
Leptus (L.) delijanensis: KHADEMI, SABOORI & HAKIMITABAR, 2015: 929
Type locality: Delijan
Distribution: Iran
Host: Acrididae indet. (Insecta: Orthoptera)
- Leptus (L.) edwini* Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (L.) edwini HAITLINGER, 2009b: 145
Type locality: Tenerife, Fuente Joco
- Distribution: Canary Islands
Host: *Laparocerus tessellates* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)
- Leptus (L.) eslamizadehi* Saboori, 2002 – Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)
- Leptus (L.) hammameticus* Haitlinger, 1998 – Sicily (HAITLINGER, 2012)
Syn. *Leptus ignotus* (Oudemans, 1903) = *L. molochinus* (C.L. Koch, 1837) (ŁAYDANOWICZ & MAKOL, 2010)
- Leptus (L.) josifovi* Beron, 1975 – Albania, Montenegro (HAITLINGER, 2012)
- Leptus (Leptus) kattikus* Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (Leptus) kattikus HAITLINGER, 2009e: 61; MAKOL et al., 2012: 67
Type locality: Nepal,
Distribution: Nepal, Vietnam
Hosts: from herbaceous plants; Phasmida
- Leptus (L.) korneli* Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (L.) korneli HAITLINGER, 2009a: 1152
Type locality: Sal Island, 3 km north of Espargos
Distribution: Rep. of Cape Verde
Host: from herbaceous plants
- Leptus (L.) longipilis* (Berlese, 1910) – Finland (GABRYŚ, ROLAND, MAKOL & LEHTINEN, 2009)
- Leptus (L.) lugenus* Kamran (larval)
Leptus (L.) lugenus KAMRAN, 2009: 81
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan
- Leptus (L.) mariae* Haitlinger, 1987 – Estonia, Latvia (HAITLINGER, 2010a), Macedonia (HAITLINGER,)
- Leptus (L.) maxorata* Haitlinger (larval)
Leptus (L.) maxorata HAITLINGER, 2009b: 141
Type locality: Fuerteventura, Malpais Grande
Distribution: Canary Islands
Host: *Herpisticus calvus* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)
- Leptus (L.) multanensis* Kamran (larval)
Leptus (L.) multanensis KAMRAN, 2009: 89
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan

Leptus (L.) millipediis Southcott, 1992

Madeira. Known from this island on Diplopoda, but recorded by HAITLINGER (2009b) from *Laparocerus (Atlantis) lamellipes* and *L. (A.) noctivagans* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae).

Leptus (L.) molochinus (C.L. Koch, 1837) – Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Leptus (L.) multisolenidiae Mayoral et Barranco

Leptus (L.) multisolenidiae MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011b: 413

Type locality: Kaw mountain, Cayenne

Distribution: French Guiana

Host: *Episomacris gruneri* (Orthoptera: Acrididae)

Leptus (L.) nikanori Haitlinger, 1998 – Costa Rica (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011a), French Guiana (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011b)

Leptus (L.) pakistanensis Kamran, Afzal, Bashir, Raza et Saeed Khan (larval)

Leptus pakistanensis KAMRAN, AFZAL, BASHIR, RAZA & SAEED KHAN, 2009: 17

Type locality: five km south of district Okara (Punjab)

Distribution: Pakistan

Host: *Aphis* sp. (Homoptera: Aphididae)

Leptus (L.) phalangii (De Geer, 1778)(larval, postlarval)

Acarus phalangii De Geer, 1778 – 117

Leptus phalangii: Gabryś, 1991: 104;

Rhyncholophus nemorum C.L. Koch, 1836: fasc.1, t.4

Leptus nemorum: Oudemans, 1914: 16 (more synonyms in MAKOL, GABRYŚ & ŁAYDANOWICZ, 2011)

Leptus beroni Fain, 1991: 109

Leptus holmiai Southcott, 1992: 60

Leptus (L.) planaltensis Haitlinger, Šundić et Pompermaier (larval)

Leptus (L.) planaltensis HAITLINGER, ŠUNDIĆ & POMPERMAIER, 2017: 879

Type locality: 30 km NE of Brasilia

Distribution: Brazil

Leptus (L.) salicus Haitlinger (larval)

Leptus (L.) salicus HAITLINGER, 2009a: 150

Type locality: Sal Island

Distribution: Rep. of Cape Verde

Host: Orthoptera indet.

Leptus (L.) sulawesicus Haitlinger (larval)

Leptus (L.) sulawesicus HAITLINGER, 2011: 53

Type locality: Sulawesi, Kietekiesu, n. Rantepao

Distribution: Indonesia (Sulawesi)

Host: from herbaceous plants

Leptus (L.) tenerificus Haitlinger (larval)

Leptus (L.) tenerificus HAITLINGER, 2009b: 147

Type locality: Tenerife, Granadilla, Las Vegas

Distribution: Canary Islands

Host: *Laparocerus fernandezi* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae)

Leptus (L.) veletae Małkol et Wohltmann, 2012 (nom. nov. pro *Leptus incertus* Gabryś, 2000)

Callidosomatinae

According to WOHLTMANN & MAKOL (2012), *Abrolophus* Berlese, 1891 is the adult form of *Hauptmannia* Oudemans, 1910.

Caeculisoma argus Vitzthum, 1926 – species status by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 17 (for *C. argus argus*)

Caeculisoma carmenae Haitlinger (larval)

Caeculisoma carmenae HAITLINGER, 2008d: 139

Caeculisoma (C.) carmenae Haitlinger: BERON, 2008: 128

Type locality: Rep. of South Africa, Port Elizabeth

Distribution: South Africa

Host: from herbaceous plants

Caeculisoma io Southcott, 1961

Formerly *Caeculisoma argus io*, full status as species by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 17

Callidosoma selmae Costa, Klompen, Dos Santos, Favretto et Pepato

Callidosoma selmae COSTA, KLOMPEN, DOS SANTOS, FAVRETTO & PEPATO, 2017: 42

Type locality: Brazil

Distribution: Brazil

Callidosoma susanae Clark

Callidosoma susanae CLARK, 2014: 177

Type locality: Southern Alps

Distribution: New Zealand

Host: from recent glacial outwash in a braided river bed

Momorangia binaloudensis Noei et Saboori

- Momorangia binaloudensis* NOEI & SABOORI, 2015: 790
Type locality: Khorasan Razavi province, Binaloud Mountain, Shirbad
Distribution: Iran
Host: *Apamea impedita* (Christoph) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)
- Momorangia chambersi* Clark
Momorangia chambersi CLARK, 2014: 186
Type locality: Southern Alps
Distribution: New Zealand
Host: from recent glacial outwash in a braided river bed
- Neomomorangia* Fain et Santiago-Blay, 1993 – full genus status (CLARK, 2014)
- Abrolophinae** Witte, 1995
- Abrolophus aitapensis* (Southcott, 1948) – Guadeloupe (HAITLINGER, 2011b); Lombok (HAITLINGER, 2011: 48)
- Abrolophus alfalfus* Kamran (larval)
Abrolophus alfalfus KAMRAN, 2009: 127
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan
- Abrolophus angustum* (Evans, 1953)
Formerly *Balaustium angustum*, transferred to *Abrolophus* by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 16
- Abrolophus anzelmi* Haitlinger et Łupicki (larval)
Abrolophus anzelmi HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2013: 682
Type locality: Sicily
Distribution: Sicily
- Abrolophus artemisiae* (Schrank, 1803) – Finland (GABRYŚ, ROLAND, MAKOL & LEHTINEN, 2009)
- Abrolophus balkanicus* Haitlinger et Šundić
Abrolophus balkanicus HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 1019
Type locality:
Distribution: Montenegro
- Abrolophus bipilum* (Meyer et Ryke, 1959)
Formerly *Balaustium bipilum*, transferred to *Abrolophus* by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 16
- Abrolophus bohadani* Kamran (larval)
- Abrolophus bohadani* KAMRAN, 2009: 135
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan
- Abrolophus faisalabadensis* Kamran
Abrolophus faisalabadensis KAMRAN, 2009: 136
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan
- Abrolophus hieronimi* Haitlinger et Łupicki
Abrolophus hieronimi HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2013: 42; MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 16
Type locality: San Martin nr. Palermo, Sicily
Distribution: Italy (Sicily)
- Abrolophus kazimierae* (Haitlinger, 1986) – Austria, Italy (HAITLINGER, 2009a)(new comb.), Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)
- Abrolophus khanjanii* (Haitlinger et Saboori, 1996) – Pakistan (KAMRAN, 2009)
- Abrolophus kotorensis* (Haitlinger, 2007) – Albania, Montenegro, Sicily (HAITLINGER, 2012) = *Abrolophus silesiacus* (Haitlinger, 1986) = *Abrolophus norvegicus* (Thor, 1900)
- Abrolophus montenegrinus* Saboori, Šundić et Pešić
Abrolophus montenegrinus SABOORI, ŠUNDIĆ & PEŠIĆ, 2012: 54
Type locality: bank of Krupac Lake, Nikšić
Distribution: Montenegro
Host: off host on grasses
- Abrolophus norvegicus* (Thor, 1900) – Neotype from N. Germany (WOHLTMANN & MAKOL, 2012)
Syn. *Hauptmannia silesiacus* Haitlinger, 1986: 189; Type locality: Wrocław – Swojec, Poland. Syn. by WOHLTMANN & MAKOL (2012).
Syn. *Hauptmannia amilberti* Haitlinger, 2010b: 5 (Type locality: Altnyaka n. Kemer; 7 km N of Cavus Koy, 11 km N Olympus; Kemer, Turkey)
Syn. *Hauptmannia dagmarae* Haitlinger, 2012: 42; Type locality: Lago di Pian del Leone (Sicily), from herbaceous plants and from larva of undet. Hemiptera. Syn. by Wohltmann & Małkol (2012).
Syn. *Hauptmannia striata* Saboori, Šundić & Pešić, 2011: 64; Type locality: Vranjske Njive, bank of Zeta River, Podgorica (Montenegro). Syn. by Wohltmann & Małkol (2012).
Syn. *Abrolophus neobrevicollis* Zhang et Goldarazena, 1996: 127; Type locality: Pitillas,

- Navarra, Spain. Syn. by Wohltmann & Maĳkol (2012).
 Supplement to distribution: Belgium (HAITLINGER, 2008), Romania (HAITLINGER, 2009d), Estonia, Latvia (HAITLINGER, 2010), Sicily (HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2015b), Montenegro (SABOORI, ŠUNDIĆ, PEŠIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2011, sub *Hauptmannia striata*).
- Abrolophus nymindegabicus*** Haitlinger
Abrolophus nymindegabicus HAITLINGER, 2008c: 53
 Type locality: Denmark, Nymindegab
 Distribution: Denmark, Sweden
- Abrolophus petanovicae*** Saboori, Šundić et Pešić
Abrolophus petanovicae SABOORI, ŠUNDIĆ & PEŠIĆ, 2012: 57; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015: 584
 Type locality: Skadar Lake, Murići (Montenegro)
 Distribution: Montenegro, Serbia
 Host: on grasses .
- Abrolophus pyrillus*** Kamran (larval)
Abrolophus pyrillus KAMRAN, 2009: 144
 Type locality: Punjab
 Distribution: Pakistan
- Abrolophus quisquiliarus*** (Hermann, 1804) – Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012); Finland (GABRYŚ et al., 2009)
- Abrolophus quisquiliarus kiejestuti*** (Haitlinger, 2007) – Romania (HAITLINGER, 2009d)
- Abrolophus stanislavae*** (Haitlinger, 1986) – Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012)(comb. in MAĳKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 16)
- Abrolophus thripsus*** Kamran (larval)
Abrolophus thripsus KAMRAN, 2009: 151
 Type locality: Punjab
 Distribution: Pakistan
- Abrolophus vignae*** (Meyer et Ryke, 1959)(for *Balaustium vignae*, see MAĳKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 16)
- Abrolophus wratislaviensis*** (Haitlinger, 1986) – Austria, Bulgaria, Estonia, Italy, Latvia, Romania (HAITLINGER, 2009a, 2009d, 2010a); Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)
- Charletonia bahaensis*** Kamran et Alatawi (larval)
Charletonia bahaensis KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2014: 85
 Type locality: Saudi Arabia
 Distribution: Saudi Arabia
Charletonia baluchestanica Tashakor et Hakimitabar (larval)
Charletonia baluchestanica TASHAKOR & HAKIMITABAR, 2015: 198
 Type locality: Behshahr City, Ghalehpayan vil-
 lage
 Distribution: Iran
 Host: *Ochrilidia* sp. (Orthoptera: Acrididae)
- Charletonia behbahanensis*** Haitlinger et Saboori (larval)
Charletonia behbahanensis HAITLINGER & SABOORI, 2008: 74
 Type locality: Behbahan
 Distribution: Iran
 Host: *Dociostaurus maroccanus* (Orthoptera: Acrididae)
- Charletonia behshahriensis*** Hakimitabar et Saboori (larval)
Charletonia behshahriensis HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI, 2014: 295
 Type locality: Behshahr City, Ghalehpayan vil-
 lage
 Distribution: Iran
 Host: *Tettigonia* sp. (Orthoptera: Tettigoniidae)
- Charletonia bojnordensis*** Haitlinger et Saboori (larval)
Charletonia bojnordensis HAITLINGER & SABOORI, 2008: 77
 Type locality: Bojnord
 Distribution: Iran
 Host: indet. (Coleoptera: Buprestidae)
- Charletonia bucephalia*** Beron, 1975 – Montenegro (ŠUNDIĆ & PAJOVIĆ, 2013, redescription)
- Charletonia cameroonensis*** Haitlinger et Kekeunou (larval)
Charletonia cameroonensis Haitlinger et Kekeunou, in HAITLINGER, KEKEUNOU & ŁUPICKI, 2014: 40
 Type locality: Cameroon,
 Distribution: Cameroon
 Host: *Zonocerus variegatus* (Orthoptera: Pyrgomorphidae)
- Charletonia cardinalis*** (Pallas, 1772) – Latvia, Lithuania (HAITLINGER, 2010a), Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012)

Charletonia domawiti Haitlinger, 2004 – Costa Rica (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011a), French Guiana (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011b)

Charletonia elbasani Šundić, Haitlinger et Milošević (larval)

Charletonia elbasani ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER & MILOŠEVIĆ, 2017: 564

Type locality: Elbasan

Distribution: Albania

Host: from herbaceous plants

Charletonia farajji Noei, Saboori et Hajizadeh (larval)

Charletonia farajji NOEI, SABOORI & HAJIZADEH, 2015: 442

Type locality: Lowshan, Rudbar, Rostamabad cities, Guilan Province

Distribution: Iran

Host: Orthoptera indet.

Charletonia gabini (Haitlinger, 2004) – Kenya (CLARK, 2014, for *Momorangia gabini* Haitlinger)

Charletonia jolantae Haitlinger, 1986 = *Ch. volzi* (Oudemans, 1910)(HAITLINGER, 2007c)

Charletonia kosensis Haitlinger (larval)

Charletonia kosensis HAITLINGER, 2016: 1010

Type locality: Kos

Distribution: Greece

Charletonia kovalamensis Haitlinger (larval)

Charletonia kovalamensis HAITLINGER, 2007c: 76

Type locality: India, Kovalam; Sri Lanka, Mount Lavinia

Distribution: India, Nepal, Sri Lanka

Host: Orthoptera indet.

Charletonia krendowskii (Feider, 1954) – Italy, Macedonia (HAITLINGER, 2009a), Albania (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015)

Charletonia lankensis Southcott, 1988 from India (HAITLINGER, 2007c) and from Sri Lanka (= *Ch. keralicus* Ramaraju & Mohanasundaram, 1998)

Charletonia postojnensis Haitlinger (larval)

Charletonia postojnensis HAITLINGER, 2011: 28

Type locality: Postojna

Distribution: Slovenia

Charletonia ramoni Haitlinger (larval)

Charletonia ramoni HAITLINGER, 2007: 78

Type locality: Nepal

Distribution: Nepal

Charletonia salazari Mayoral et Barranco

Charletonia salazari MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011: 223

Type locality: Colonia Palmareña, San Ramón, Alajuela

Distribution: Costa Rica

Host: *Scopiorinus mucronatus* (Orthoptera, Tettigoniidae, Pseudophyllinae).

Charletonia shahriari Saboori, Azimi et Shirdel (larval)

Charletonia shahriari SABOORI, AZIMI & SHIRDEL, 2012: 34

Type locality: Dizaj Olia village (38° 8.043' N, 46° 13.041' E, ~1470 m a.s.l.), Tabriz, East Azarbaijan province.

Distribution: Iran

Host: undetermined cercopid (Homoptera: Cercopidae)

Charletonia shiroyama Yaita, Kato et Toriyama, 1961 – Laos, Thailand (HAITLINGER, 2007c); Java (HAITLINGER, 2011)

Syn.: ***Charletonia sureshi*** (Ramaraju et Mohanasundaram, 1998) = *Ch. volzi* (Oudemans, 1910)(HAITLINGER, 2007c)

Charletonia stekolnikovi Hakimitabar et Saboori (larval)

Charletonia stekolnikovi HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI, 2011: 40

Type locality: Taleghan city, 214 m, Tehran province

Distribution: Iran

Host: from herbaceous plants

Charletonia talebii Sedghi, Saboori et Hakimitabar (larval)

Charletonia talebii SEDGHI, SABOORI & HAKIMITABAR, 2010: 335

Type locality: Jahrom

Distribution: Iran

Host: undet. Cicadellidae (Heteroptera)

Charletonia terianae Hakimitabar, Saboori et Seiedy

Charletonia terianae HAKIMITABAR, SABOORI & SEIEDY, 2013: 164

Type locality: Tehran, Karaj

Distribution: Iran
Host: undet. Phalangiidae (Opiliones), undet. Cheliferidae (Pseudoscorpiones), Araneae

Charletonia villingensis Haitlinger (larval)
Charletonia villingensis HAITLINGER, 2007c: 73
Type locality: Villing
Distribution: Maldives
Host: from herbaceous plants

Charletonia volzi (Oudemans, 1910) – Laos, Malaysia, Thailand (HAITLINGER, 2007c)

[***Grandjeanella bella*** Zhang, 1996 is considered part of genus *Nagoricanelle* Haitlinger by SABOORI et al. (2016)]

Grandjeanella londaensis Haitlinger
Grandjeanella londaensis HAITLINGER, 2011: 50
Type locality: Londa n. Rantepao
Distribution: Indonesia
Host: from herbaceous plants

Grandjeanella macfarlanei Clark
Grandjeanella macfarlanei CLARK, 2014: 191
Type locality: Southern Alps
Distribution: New Zealand
Host: from recent glacial outwash in a braided river bed

Grandjeanella multisetosa Zhang et Goldarazena, 1996 – Hungary, Romania, Macedonia, San Marino (HAITLINGER, 2009a, 2009d, 2012)

Genus ***Marantelophus*** Haitlinger
Marantelophus HAITLINGER, 2011: 50
Type species: *Marantelophus alaperti* Haitlinger, 2011

Marantelophus ainae (Haitlinger, 2002) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Mallorca)

Marantelophus alaperti Haitlinger
Marantelophus alaperti HAITLINGER, 2011: 50
Type locality: Sulawesi, Marante n. Rantepao
Distribution: Indonesia (Sulawesi)

Marantelophus bella (Zhang, 1996) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Iran and Turkey); Turkey, ex *Parlatoria oleae* (Homoptera: Diaspididae) (SABOORI & COBANOGU, 2010), transferred to *Nagoricanelle* by SABOORI et al. (2016)

Marantelophus dubifurcatus Xu, Yi et Jin
Marantelophus dubifurcatus XU, YI & JIN, 2017:
Type locality: China
Distribution: China
Hosts: *Cacopsyllus* sp. (Homoptera: Psyllidae), Psocoptera

Marantelophus emanueli (Haitlinger)
Grandjeanella emanueli HAITLINGER, 2010b: 56
Marantelophus emanueli (Haitlinger): KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2015:
Type locality: Elmali, 1200 m
Distribution: Turkey
Host: from herbaceous plants

Marantelophus haitlingeri (Goldarazena et Zhang, 1997) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Spain)

Marantelophus kamalii (Saboori et Atamehr, 2000) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Iran). Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2014: 40)

Marantelophus multisetosa (Zhang et Goldarazena, 1996) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Romania, San Marino, Spain, Turkey and Ukraine)

Marantelophus ostovani (Haitlinger et Saboori, 1996) – transferred from *Grandjeanella* by HAITLINGER, 2011 (Iran)

Marantelophus rudaensis (Haitlinger)
Hauptmannia rudaensis HAITLINGER, 1986: 182
Rudaemia rudaensis Haitlinger: HAITLINGER, 2000: 386
Abrolophus rudaensis (Haitlinger): MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2012:

Marantelophus rudaensis (Haitlinger, 1986) – Montenegro (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2014: 40)

Marantelophus sanandajensis Hakimitabar et Saboori

Marantelophus sanandajensis Hakimitabar et Saboori, in: HAKIMITABAR, GHOBARI & SABOORI, 2015: 226

Type locality: Koushk Bala village, Chalous road, Karaj

Distribution: Iran
Host: from unidentified Thysanoptera and Aphididae (Homoptera)

Genus ***Nagoricanelle*** Haitlinger (larval)

- Nagoricanelle* Haitlinger, 2009c: 40
Type species: *Nagoricanelle egoni* Haitlinger, 2009
- Nagoricanelle arabellae*** Haitlinger (larval)
Nagoricanelle arabellae: HAITLINGER, 2009c: 41
Type locality: 3 km north of Espargos, Sal Island
Distribution: the Republic of Cape Verde
Host: from herbaceous plants
- Nagoricanelle bella*** (Zhang, 1996) – combination created by SABOORI et al. (2016) from *Grandjeanelle bella* Zhang, 1996 = *Marantelophus bella* (Zhang)
- Nagoricanelle egoni*** Haitlinger (larval)
Nagoricanelle egoni HAITLINGER, 2009c: 46
Type locality: Staro Nagoričane n. Kumanovo
Distribution: the Republic of Cape Verde
Host: from herbaceous plants
- Nagoricanelle salehi*** Kamran et Alatawi (larval)
Nagoricanelle salehi KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2015: 196
Type locality: Saudi Arabia
Distribution: Saudi Arabia
- Genus ***Pukakia*** Clark
Pukakia CLARK, 2014: 198
Type species: *Pukakia aoraki* Clark, 2014
- Pukakia aoraki*** Clark
Pukakia aoraki CLARK, 2014: 198
Type locality: Southern Alps
Distribution: New Zealand
Host: from recent glacial outwash in a braided river bed
- Balaustiinae**
Genus ***Balaustium*** von Heyden, 1826
= *Guatustium* Haitlinger, 2000 – synonymized by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013
= *Palenquustum* Haitlinger, 2000 – synonymized by FUENTES QUINTERO et al., 2014
- Balaustium biljanae*** (Haitlinger, 2000)
Formerly *Guatustium biljanae*, synonymized by MAKOL & WOHLTMANN, 2013: 17
- Balaustium biscutalae*** Mayoral et Barranco (larval)
Balaustium biscutalae MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2009: 1161
Type locality: Amoladeras. P.N. Cabo de Gata
- Nijar. T.M. de Nijar, Almeria
Distribution: Spain
- Balaustium hernandezi*** Mağkol, Arijs et Wäckers
Balaustium hernandezi Mağkol, Arijs & Wäckers, 2012: 2
Type locality: Spain
Distribution: Spain
- Balaustium kacperi*** Haitlinger, 1996 – Latvia (HAITLINGER, 2010a)
- Balaustium leanderi*** (HAITLINGER, 2000) – formerly *Palenquustum* Haitlinger, 2000 – synonymized by FUENTES QUINTERO et al., 2014, 2015
- Balaustium nikae*** Haitlinger, 1996 – Bulgaria (HAITLINGER, 2009d), Italy (HAITLINGER, 2009a), Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012)
- Balaustium yousifi*** Kamran et Alatawi (larval)
Balaustium yousifi KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2014a: 90
Type locality: 5 km Taif Road, Baha
Distribution: Saudi Arabia
- Genus ***Madinahustium*** Kamran et Alatawi
Madinahustium Kamran & Alatawi, 2016: 79
Type species: *Madinahustium acaiaum* Kamran & Alatawi, 2016
- Madinahustium acaciaum*** Kamran et Alatawi
Madinahustium acaciaum Kamran & Alatawi, 2016: 79
Type locality: Saudi Arabia
Distribution: Saudi Arabia
- Moldoustium haitlingeri*** Noei, Saboori et Šundić (larval)
Moldoustium haitlingeri NOEI, SABOORI & ŠUNDIĆ, 2013: 264
Type locality: Loshan city, 1339 m, Guilan Province; paratypes from Montenegro, Plavnica, nr. Shkodar Lake
Distribution: Iran, Montenegro
Host: soil
- Genus ***Monteustium*** Haitlinger et Šundić
Monteustium Haitlinger & Šundić, 2015: 2015
Type species: *Monteustium* Haitlinger & Šundić, 2015
- Monteustium marezensis*** Haitlinger et Šundić

Monteustium marezensis Haitlinger & Šundić,
2015: 1108
Type locality: Montenegro
Distribution: Montenegro

Pollux jhangensis Kamran

Pollux jhangensis KAMRAN, 2009: 108
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan

Pollux kovalamicus Haitlinger, 2002 – Pakistan
(KAMRAN, 2009), Indonesia (HAITLINGER, 2010)
Syn. *Pollux walii* KAMRAN, AFZAL & RAZA, 2010
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan

Pollux okaraensis Kamran

Pollux okaraensis KAMRAN, 2009: 100
Type locality: Punjab,
Distribution: Pakistan

Pollux punctatus Kamran

Pollux punctatus KAMRAN, 2009: 115
Type locality: Punjab
Distribution: Pakistan

Pollux workandae Southcott, 1961 – Pakistan
(KAMRAN & BASHIR, 2013)

Fossil Calyptostomatoidea and Erythraeoidea

Calyptostomatidae

Calyptostoma katyae Konikiewicz, Wohltmann
et Małkol
Calyptostoma katyae KONIKIEWICZ,
WOHLTMANN & MAŁKOL, 2016: 337
Type locality: Baltic Amber

Smarididae

Fessonia grabenhorsti Bartel, Konikiewicz,
Małkol, Wohltmann et Dunlop
Fessonia grabenhorsti BARTEL, KONIKIEWICZ,
MAŁKOL, WOHLTMANN & DUNLOP, 2015: 653
Type locality: Baltic and Bitterfeld Amber

Fessonia groehni Bartel, Konikiewicz, Małkol,
Wohltmann et Dunlop
Fessonia groehni BARTEL, KONIKIEWICZ,
MAŁKOL, WOHLTMANN & DUNLOP, 2015: 655
Type locality: Baltic and Bitterfeld Amber

Fessonia wunderlichii Bartel, Konikiewicz,

Małkol, Wohltmann et Dunlop
Fessonia wunderlichii BARTEL, KONIKIEWICZ,
MAŁKOL, WOHLTMANN & DUNLOP, 2015: 649
Type locality: Baltic and Bitterfeld Amber
Erythraeidae

Genus ***Pararainbowia*** Dunlop

Pararainbowia DUNLOP, 2007: 96
Type species: *Pararainbowia martilli* Dunlop, 2007

Pararainbowia martilli Dunlop

Pararainbowia martilli DUNLOP, 2007: 96 –
Brazil, from the Early Cretaceous (Aptian) Crato
Formation from Ceará Stat.

**Distribution of Calyptostomatoidea and
Erythraeoidea (suppl.)**

EUROPE

Albania (HAITLINGER, 2012a; HAITLINGER
& ŠUNDIĆ, 2014, 2015; ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER &
MILOŠEVIĆ, 2016) – *Erythraeus (Erythraeus) al-*
banicus, *Abrolophus kotorensis*, *Leptus (L.) josifovi*,
Charletonia elbasani, *Ch. krendowskyi*

Austria (HAITLINGER, 2007d, 2009a) –
Abrolophus pseudolongicollis, *A. kazimierae*, *A. wrat-*
islaviensis, *Balaustium nikaie*, *Erythraeus (E.) gertru-*
dae, *Leptus (L.) mariae*

Belgium (HAITLINGER, 2008c) – *Abrolophus*
norvegicus

Bulgaria (HAITLINGER, 2009d) – *Balaustium*
nikaie, *Charletonia cardinalis*, *Erythraeus (E.) smoly-*
anensis, *E. (Zaracarus) budapestensis*, *Abrolophus ka-*
zimierae, *A. wratislaviensis*

Crimea (SABOORI, KHAUSTOV, HAKIMITABAR &
HAJIQANBAR, 2009) – *Makolia crimeaensis*

Denmark (HAITLINGER, 2008c) – *Abrolophus*
nymindegabicus

Estonia (HAITLINGER, 2010a) – *Abrolophus nor-*
vegicus, *A. wratislaviensis*, *Leptus (L.) mariae*, *L. (L.)*
molochinus, *L. (L.) miromiri*, *Erythraeus (E.) kuyperi*

Finland (GABRYŚ, ROLAND, MAŁKOL &
LEHTINEN, 2009) – **Smarididae:** *Hirstiosoma latreillei*;
Erythraeidae: *Abrolophus artemisiae*, *A. miniatus*, *A.*
norvegicus, *A. brevicollis*, *A. quisquiliarus*, *Charletonia*
cardinalis, *Curteria episcopalis*, *Erythraeus cinereus*,
Kamertonia polonica, *Leptus longipilis*, *L. rubricatus*,
L. molochinus (= *L. ignotus*)

Germany (WOHLTMANN, 2010, WOHLTMANN
& MAŁKOL, 2012) – *Abrolophus norvegicus* (neotype),
Phanolophus oedipodarum

Greece (ANTONATOS & EMMANOUEL, 2014) –
Erythraeidae

Hungary (HAITLINGER, 2007d, 2009a) – *Grandjeanella multisetosa*

Italy (HAITLINGER, 2007d, 2009a, 2012) – *Abrolophus mirabelae*, *A. kazimierae*, *A. wratislaviensis*, *Balaustium nikae*, *Charletonia austiensis*, *Ch. krendowskyi*, *Ch. berlesiana*, *Ch. cardinalis*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *malwinae*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *phalangii* (syn. *L. beroni*), *L.* (*L.*) *molochinus*, *L.* (*L.*) *slivovi*, *Marantelophus multisetosa*

Sicily (HAITLINGER, 2012b, HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2014b, 2015, HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2013a, b, 2015) – **Calyptostomatidae**: *Calyptostoma velutinum*; **Erythraeidae**: *Abrolophus anzelmi*, *A. norvegicus* (= *Hauptmannia dagmarae*), *Leptus hammameticus*, *L. chiusicus*, *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *adrianicus*, *E. (Z.) monrealicus*

Latvia (HAITLINGER, 2010a) – *Abrolophus norvegicus*, *A. wratislaviensis*, *Charletonia cardinalis*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *kuyperi*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *mariae*, *Balaustium kacperi*

Lituania (HAITLINGER, 2010a) – *Charletonia cardinalis*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *kuyperi*

Luxemburg (HAITLINGER, 2008c) – *Leptus* (*L.*) *trimaculatus*

Macedonia (HAITLINGER, 2009d, 2012a) – *Charletonia krendowskyi*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *cinereus* (= *jowitae*), *Leptus* (*L.*) *mariae*, *L. (L.) molochinus* (= *ignotus*)

Montenegro (SABOORI, PEŠIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2008; SABOORI et al., 2011, 2012; HAITLINGER, 2012a; NOEL, SABOORI et al., 2013; ŠUNDIĆ & PAJOVIĆ, 2012, 2013; ŠUNDIĆ, 2014; ŠUNDIĆ & HAITLINGER, 2015; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2014A, 2015a, 2015c, 2016, 2017) – **Smarididae**: *Hirstiosoma amfilohijeji*; **Erythraeidae**: *Abrolophus montenegrinus*, *A. balkanicus*, *A. norvegicus* (= *Hauptmannia striata*), *A. kotozensis*, *A. petanovicae*, *A. wratislaviensis*, *Balaustium nikae*, *Charletonia bucephalia*, *Erythraeus* (*Z.*) *aydinicus*, *E. (E.) budapestensis*, *E. (Z.) cf. ueckermanni*, *E. (Z.) tuzicus*, *E. (E.) ankaraiscus*, *E. (E.) smolyanensis*, *E. (E.) southcotti*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *josifovi*, *L. (L.) biljanae*, *L. (L.) eslamizadehi*, *L. (L.) molochinus*, *Italustium eframi*, *Marantelophus kamalii*, *M. rudaensis*, *Moldoustium haitlingeri*, *Monteustium marezensis*

Poland (GABRYŚ & MAKOL, 1997; KLOSIŃSKA, FELSKA, ŁAYDANOWICZ & MAKOL, 2009) – *Abrolophus norvegicus*

Portugal

Azorean Islands (MCNEIL & TREAT, 1992; LORENZO – CARBALLA et al., 2011) – *Leptus killingtoni*

Romania (HAITLINGER, 2009d) – *Abrolophus quisquiliaris kiejestuti*, *A. norvegicus*, *Balaustium nikae*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *jowitae*, *E. (E.) monikae*, *Grandjeanella*

multisetosa, *Abrolophus kazimierae*, *A. wratislaviensis*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *mariae*

San Marino (HAITLINGER, 2007d, 2009a) – *Balaustium nikae*, *Grandjeanella multisetosa*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *molochinus* (= *ignotus*)

Serbia (HAITLINGER, 2012; ŠUNDIĆ, 2014; ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER, PETANOVIĆ, JOVICIĆ & HAKIMITABAR, 2015; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015) – **Calyptostomatidae**: *Calyptostoma velutinum*; **Erythraeidae**: *Abrolophus petanovicae*, *A. quisquiliaris*, *A. stanislavae*, *Balaustium nikae*, *Charletonia cardinalis*, *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *budapestensis*

Slovenia (HAITLINGER, 2011b) – *Charletonia postojnensis*, *Abrolophus podoresensis*

Spain (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2017; WOHLTMANN, 2010; MAKOL, ARIJS & WÄCKERS, 2012) – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *ruizporterae*, *Forania sendrai*, *Balaustium biscutalae*, *B. hernandezii*, *Phanolophus oedipodarum*; **Smarididae**: *Sphaerotarsus baenai*

Canary Islands (HAITLINGER, 2009b) – *Leptus* (*L.*) *canaricus* *L. (L.) edwini*, *L. (L.) maxorata*, *L. (L.) tenerificus*

Sweden (HAITLINGER, 2008b, 2008c) – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *jowitae*, *Leptus trimaculatus*, *Abrolophus nymindegabicus*

Turkey (entire) (HAITLINGER, 2010b; SABOORI & COBANOGU, 2010) – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *adanaensis*, *E. (E.) elmalicus*, *E. (E.) hilariae*, *E. (Zaracarus) budapestensis*, *E. (Z.) passidonicus*, *Nagoricanelle bella*, *Marantelophus emanueli*, *Abrolophus amilberti*, *Zhangielli* (= *Curteria*); *Zhangielli duzgunesae* Saboori et al., 2007 = *Curteria duzgunesae* (syn. by SABOORI et al., 2009)

AFRICA

Cameroon (HAITLINGER, KEKEUNOU & ŁUPICKI, 2014) – *Charletonia cameroonensis*, *Ch. justynae*

Cape Verde (HAITLINGER, 2009a, 2009c) – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *capeverdensis*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *korneli*, *L. (L.) salicis*

Kenya (CLARK, 2014) – *Charletonia gabini*, for *Momorangia gabini* Haitlinger, 2004

ASIA

Cambodia (HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015) – **Calyptostomatidae**: *Calyptostoma giuliae*

China (LI & FAN, 1997; ZHANG, 2010; XU, YI & JIN, 2017) – **Smarididae**: *Fessonina papillosa*; **Erythraeidae**: *Marantelophus dubifurcatus*

Cyprus (HAITLINGER & ŁUPICKI, 2011) – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *arminouensis*

India (HAITLINGER, 2007c; AGARWAL, DHIMAN & AGARWAL, 2009) – *Charletonia kovalamensis*, *Ch. lankensis*, *Leptus* sp.

Indonesia (HAITLINGER, 2010c, 2011c; HAITLINGER & ŠUNDIĆ, 2015) – **Calyptostomatidae**: *Calyptostoma marantica*; **Erythraeidae**: *Leptus* (*L.*) *sulawesicus*, *Pollux kovalamicus*

Iran (KHANJANI, UECKERMANN & UL-HASSAN, 2007; KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, NAHAD & FAYAZ, 2010; SEDGHI, SABOORI, AKRAMI & HAKIMITABAR, 2010; SEDGHI, RAVAN, etc., 2010; KHANJANI, RAISI & IZADI (2011); SABOORI, 2011; HAKIMITABAR & SABOORI, 2011; AHMADI, HAJIQANBAR & SABOORI, 2012; SABOORI, AZIMI & SHIRDEL, 2012; AZIMI, SABOORI & SHIRDEL, 2011; SABOORI, SOUKHTSARAI et al., 2012; KHANJANI, MIRMOAYEDI, FAYAZ & SHARIFIAN, 2012; HAKIMITABAR, SABOORI & SEIEDY, 2013; HAKIMITABAR, GHOBARI & SABOORI, 2013; NOEI, SABOORI et al., 2013; NOEI, SABOORI & HAJIZADEH, 2013; HAKIMITABAR, SABOORI, SAMANIPOUR & JALALIZAND, 2014; MAHMOUDI et al., 2014; NOEI & SABOORI, 2015; KHADEMI, SABOORI, AHADIYAT & HAKIMITABAR, 2015; HAITLINGER, MEHRNEJAD & SUNDIĆ, 2016) – **Calyptostomatidae**: *Calyptostoma gorganica* **Smarididae**: *Fessonia papillosa*, *Smaris maraghehiensis*; **Erythraeidae**: *Eatoniana gonabadensis*, *Eatoniana plumipes* [= *Abalakeus jahromiensis*], *Charletonia baluchestanica*, *Ch. behbahanensis*, *Ch. behshahriensis*, *Ch. bojnordensis*, *Ch. shahriari*, *Ch. stekolnikovi*, *Ch. talebii*, *Ch. terianae*, *Colleboerythraeus vosoughae*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *adanaensis*, *E. (E.) chrysoperlae*, *E. (E.) mirabi*, *E. (E.) pistacicus*, *E. (E.) populi*, *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *hafezi*, *E. (Z.) ueckermanni* (= *hamedanicus*), *E. (Z.) coleopterus*, *E. (Z.) soleimani*, *Iraniella moharrampouri*, *Leptus dilijanensis*, *Lasioerythraeus saboorii*, *Marantelophus sanandajensis*, *Momorangia binaloudensis*, *Moldoustium haitlingeri*, *Nagoricanelia bella*

Laos (HAITLINGER, 2007c) – *Charletonia shiroyama*, *Ch. volzi*

Malaysia (HAITLINGER, 2007c) – *Charletonia volzi*

Maledives (HAITLINGER, 2007c) – *Charletonia villingensis*

Nepal (HAITLINGER, 2009e) – *Charletonia ramoni*, *Ch. kovalamensis*, *Leptus* (*L.*) *astrubali*, *L. (L.) katticus*

Pakistan (KAMRAN, 2009; KAMRAN, AFZAL, RAZA, IRFANULLAH, BASHIR & AHMAD, 2009; KAMRAN, AFZAL, BASHIR, RAZA & SAEED KHAN, 2009; KAMRAN, AFZAL & BASHIR, 2013; KAMRAN & BASHIR, 2013) – *Abrolophus alfalfus*, *A. bohadani*, *A. faisalabadensis*, *A. khanjanii*, *A. pyrillus*, *A. thripsus*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *layyahensis*, *E. (E.) loomerus*, *E. (E.) shojaii*,

Erythraeus (*Zaracarus*) *longipedus*, *E. (Z.) perpusillus*, *Lasioerythraeus setarius*, *Leptus aphidius*, *L. eslamizadehi*, *L. hospeticus*, *L. lugenus*, *L. nearcticus*, *L. multanensis*, *L. pakistanensis*, *Pollux jhangensis*, *P. kovalamicus* (= *P. walli*), *P. okaraensis*, *P. punctatus*, *P. workandae*

Saudi Arabia (KAMRAN & ALATAWI, 2014, 2015, 2016) – *Abrolophus rudaensis*, *Balaustium yousifi*, *Charletonia bahaensis*, *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *uhadi*, *E. (Z.) lancifer*, *Madinahustium acaciaum*, *Marantelophus emanueli*, *Nagoricanelia salehi*

Sri Lanka (HAITLINGER, 2007c) – *Charletonia kovalamensis*, *Ch. ramoni*

Thailand (HAITLINGER, 2007c) – *Charletonia shiroyama*, *Ch. volzi*

Vietnam (MAKOL et al., 2012, HAITLINGER, 2013) – *Leptus* (*L.*) *kattikus*, *L. holgeri*

Yemen (WOHLTMANN, 2010) – *Phanolophus oedipodiarum*

NORTH AMERICA

USA (ŠUNDIĆ, HAITLINGER, MICHAUD & COLARES, 2015) – *Erythraeus* (*Erythraeus*) *aphidivorous*

Alaska (MAKOL, 2010)

SOUTH and CENTRAL AMERICA

Brazil (DUNLOP, 2007; PEREIRA, FADINI, PIKART, ZANUNCIO & SERRÃO, 2012; CLARK, 2014; SALVATIERRA & ALMEIDA, 2017; HAITLINGER, ŠUNDIĆ & POMPERMAIER, 2017; COSTA, KLOMPEN, DOS SANTOS, FAVRETTO & PEPATO, 2017) – *Leptus brasiliensis*, *L. planaltensis*, *Leptus* sp., *Callidosoma selmae*, *Neomomorangia asphaerae*. Fossil: *Pararainbowia martilli*

Colombia (MUÑOZ et al., 2009, MUÑOZ-CÁRDENAS et al., 2014, FUENTES-QUINTERO, 2015) – *Balaustium leanderi*

Costa Rica (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011a) – *Charletonia domawiti*, *Ch. salazari*, *Leptus nikanori*

French Guiana (MAYORAL & BARRANCO, 2011b) – *Charletonia domawiti*, *Leptus multisolenidiae*, *L. nikanori*

Guadeloupe (HAITLINGER, 2011a) – *Abrolophus aitapensis*, *Leptus cabareticus*

Trinidad (TOWNSEND et al., 2008) – *Leptus* sp.

Venezuela (HAITLINGER, 2008b) – *Lasioerythraeus cardonensis*

OCEANIA

Papua New Guinea (BERON, in prep.) – *Caeculisoma* (*Papuacaeculisoma*) *chapmani*, *C. (P.) novaeirlandiae*, *C. (C.) plantacionis*, *C. (C.) darwiniense*

New Zealand (CLARK, 2013, 2014) – *Erythrites otamahua*, *Callidosoma susanae*, *Momorangia cham-*

bersi, *Grandjeanella macfarlanei*, *Pukakia aoraki*

Hosts

Arachnida

Opiliones

Fam. Cranidae – Erythraeidae

Fam. Manaosbiidae – Erythraeidae

Fam. Phalangiidae – *Charletonia terianae*

Pseudoscorpiones

Fam. Cheliferidae – *Charletonia terianae*

Araneae

Mygalomorphae

Fam. Actinopodidae – *Leptus* sp.

Araneae indet. – *Charletonia terianae*

Insecta

Collembola

Fam. Sminthuridae undet. –

Collemborythraeus vosoughae

Orthoptera

Fam. Acrididae

Abracris flavolineata – *Charletonia domawiti*

Dociostaurus cf. *tartarus* – *Eatoniana gonabadensis*

Dociostaurus maroccanus – *Charletonia behbahanensis*

Episomacris gruneri – *Leptus multisolenidiae*

Ochrilidia sp. – *Charletonia baluchestanica*

Schistocerca nitens – *Charletonia domawiti*

Fam. Proscopiidae

Pseudoprosopia scabra – *Leptus nikanori*

Fam. Tettigoniidae

Anaulacomera sp. – *Leptus nikanori*

Neoconocephalus triops – *Charletonia domawiti*

Scopiorinus mucronatus – *Charletonia salazari*

Tettigonia sp. – *Charletonia behshahriensis*

Fam. Pyrgomorphidae

Zonocerus variegatus – *Charletonia cameroonensis*, *Ch. justynae*

Orthoptera indet.

Leptus (*L.*) *salicus*, *L.* (*L.*) *biljanae*

Mecoptera

Fam. Apteropanorpidae

Apteropanorpa tasmanica – *Leptus agrotis*

Odonata

Fam. Coenagrionidae

Ischnura hastata – *Leptus killingtoni*

Homoptera

Fam. Aphididae

Aphis craccivora – *Eatoniana gonabadensis*

Aphis sp. – *Leptus pakistanensis*

A. punicae – *Lasioerythraeus saboorii*

Melanaphis saccari – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *aphidivorous*

Aphididae undet. – *Marantelophus sanandajensis*

Fam. Lophopidae

Pyrilla perpusilla – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *perpusillus*

Fam. Psyllidae

Agonosцена pistaciae – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *pistacicus*

Cacopsylla sp. – *Marantelophus dubifurcatus*

Fam. Cicadidae

Undet. – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *hafezi*

Fam. Cicadellidae

Undet. – *Charletonia talebii*

Fam. Diaspididae

Parlatoria oleae – *Nagoricanellella bella*

Fam. Cercopidae

Undet. – *Charletonia shahriari*

Heteroptera

Fam. Pyrrhocoridae

Pyrrhocoris apterus – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *ueckermanni* (= *hamedanicus*)

Fam. Coreidae

Cletus signatus – *Leptus* sp.

Fam. Nabidae

Undet. – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *hafezi*

Fam. Pentatomidae

Undet. – *Eatoniana plumipes* (= *Abalakeus jahromiensis*)

Fam. Miridae

Farsiana pistaciae – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *pistacicus*

Thysanoptera undet. – *Marantelophus sanandajensis*

Neuroptera

Fam. Chrysopidae

Chrysoperla kolthoffi – *Erythraeus* (*E.*) *chrysoperlae*, *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *soleimanii*

Undet. – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *hafezi*

Hymenoptera

Fam. Formicidae

Lasius sp. – *Makolia crimeaensis*

Tapinoma sp. – *Forania sendrai*

Lepidoptera

Fam. Noctuidae

Apamea impedita – *Momorangia binaloudensis*

Pseudaletia unipuncta – *Leptus killingtoni*

Coleoptera

Fam. Scarabaeidae

Cyphonoxia sp. – *Erythraeus* (*Z.*) *coleopterus*

Fam. Buprestidae

Undet. – *Charletonia bojnordensis*

Fam. Tenebrionidae

Eupezus rufipes – *Charletonia justinae*

Diptera

Fam. Tachinidae

Undet. – *Erythraeus* (*Zaracarus*) *hafezi*

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Acarorum Catalogus I – Първо допълнение (2008–2016)

Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

След публикуването на първия том на *Acarorum Catalogus* (BERON, 2008), бяха публикувани много нови данни за надсем. Calyptostomatoidea и Erythraeoidea (Erythraeidae, Smarididae) от мен и от мнозина полски, германски, ирански, черногорски, пакистански, испански и други колеги. Бяха описани нови таксони и извършени таксономични промени, както и допълнения в географското разпространение на тези акари. Бяха добавени 10 нови рода и повече от 120 нови вида, някои видове и 7 рода отпаднаха като синоними. Вследствие на това беше актуализиран броят на родовете и видовете в семействата: един род и девет вида Calyptostomatidae, 10 рода и 56 вида Smarididae и 57 рода и повече от 850 вида Erythraeidae. Библиографията на настоящото първо допълнение на Католага включва 166 нови и пропуснати заглавия за периода 2008-2016 (някои от тях през 2017 г.).